

DISTANCE EDUCATION AND ITS DEVELOPMENT TENDENCIES IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: *This article examines distance education and its development trends in Uzbekistan. Also, the priority directions of the development of this industry in the country and the factors affecting it were studied, and scientific proposals and practical recommendations were given.*

Keywords: *distance education, USA, information technology, GDP, computer service, e-textbook, platform, education costs, mechanism, infrastructure.*

INTRODUCTION

After the independence of Uzbekistan, as in all fields, reforms were implemented in order to develop the education system and the quality of education was improved. As a result, today, the organization of providing high-quality education to students widely utilizes modern information technologies, which are products of scientific and technological progress, as well as computers that serve as their material basis. The creation of electronic textbooks and manuals, the use of internet resources, and the promotion of software tools for distance learning have become a necessity of the time. In the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 559 of October 3, 2022 "On measures to introduce the form of distance education in higher education organizations", based on the use of information and communication technologies, regardless of the student's place of residence, providing him with the opportunity to master educational programs, determining by the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of bachelor's education courses and master's specialties where it is not possible to introduce a form of distance education, organizing distance education using a special platform or using existing platforms, in the training of personnel based on the form of distance education, the admission parameters for one bachelor's education course are determined to be no more than 300 students, for one master's specialties are determined to be no more than 30 students¹.

The above-mentioned circumstances demonstrate the relevance and importance of this research topic.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

¹ Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 559 of October 3, 2022 "On measures to introduce the form of distance education in higher education organizations"/ <https://lex.uz/docs/-6221502>

Various research methods, including statistical analysis, comparative analysis, generalization and systematic approach, were used to achieve the stated goals and objectives.

ANALYSIS AND RESULT

Today's world experience shows that the traditional day education system and forms aimed at students' creative activity and self-awareness cannot fully and deeply solve this goal. Due to the unfavorable economic situation in the republic, due to the limitation of personnel, scientific-theoretical and material-pedagogical resources in the field of education, support for the realization of distance learning technologies and the creative potential of students, expansion of their knowledge, regional education issues of providing opportunities, conditions for development of the system, organization of pedagogical work of educational institutions with talented students in local areas have been determined. Distance education, as an additional form of regular education, can solve the problems of personal learning through computer technologies.

In recent years, attention has been paid to the education system as one of the most important areas in the world. A clear example of this can be the share of GDP of developed countries' spending on the education system (Table 1).

Table 1

The share of spending on the education system of Uzbekistan and developed countries in 2022 (in relation to GDP, %) and their place in the world ranking²

№	Name of countries	GDP (billion dollars)	GDP per capita (dollars)	Education expenses (in relation to GDP, %)	Ranking of countries (by spending on education)
1.	USA	25744	77243	4.59	64
2.	China	17963	12666	3.3	100
3.	Japan	4237	33866	3.32	99
4.	Germany	4085	48593	4.53	66

² Developed by the author based on data from https://theglobaleconomy.com/rankings/education_spending/

5.	Great Britain	3081	46018	5.33	40
6.	Uzbekistan	80.4	2256	5.37	39

It can be analyzed from the table that in 2022, the GDP of the United States will be 25744 billion dollars and it will take the 1st place, and therefore it will spend 4.59% on the development of the education sector, which is 1.18 trillion dollars. Among the developed countries of Asia, Japan and China took consecutive places (99th and 100th) with 3.32% and 3.3% of education expenditure, respectively. In Germany, this indicator was 4.53%, while in Great Britain 5.33% of GDP was allocated (\$185.05 and 164.21 billion). The Republic of Uzbekistan occupies the 39th place with 5.37%. The main reason for the disproportion of the positions occupied by the states is related to the size of the GDP. Because if we take the USA, the share of the education sector remains small due to the large GDP.

After the independence of the republic, great attention was paid to increasing the coverage and production of distance education and reducing the unemployment rate of the population at the same time. In the 46 of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 No. PD-60 "On the Development Strategy of the New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" the task of further expanding the possibility of obtaining higher education without separating young people from production by introducing the form of distance education in the higher education system is set³.

In the advanced age of our society, it is desirable to make the educational process more interesting and pleasant for the students, using the opportunities of scientific and technical innovations, the Internet and new technologies, without being limited to previous methodical manuals. In our republic today, great importance is attached to the development of computer technologies and the Internet.

In the distance education method, even if the teacher and the student are separated by a distance, constant communication is maintained. E-mail and Internet technologies are widely used as a way to control this teaching.

World experience has shown that distance education is important in improving the literacy and thinking of the population. Later, as a result of studying the advantages and disadvantages of this field, the implementation of distance education in our country was determined as one of the priority issues. (Figure 1)

³ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 No. PF-60 "On the new development strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026".

Figure 1. Advantages and disadvantages of distance education⁴

As shown in Figure 1, the advantages of distance education are more than its disadvantages, and it should be emphasized that the development of this field is the optimal way to stabilize the production network of the economy and improve the social condition of the population.

Pursuant to the 6th purpose of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-158 of September 11, 2023 "On Uzbekistan - 2030 Strategy", the task of establishing 14 regional professional training centers, increasing the share of qualified pedagogic personnel to 50%, and the share of distance or mixed training courses to 30% was set⁵.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

⁴ Developed by the author as a result of research.

⁵ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 11, 2023 No. PF-158 "On the strategy of "Uzbekistan - 2030"" / www.lex.uz

As a result of the analysis and research carried out above, the following are proposed for the development of distance education in Uzbekistan:

- To support the state policy aimed at the development of distance education programs, the achievements in the field of information and communication technologies, as well as the modernization of the education sector.
- Investing in the necessary infrastructure and resources to support the growth of distance education in Uzbekistan.
- Improve Internet connectivity, train teachers in online pedagogy, and establish robust quality assurance mechanisms.
- To further strengthen the development of distance education programs by strengthening public-private partnership and cooperation with international organizations.
- Making full use of distance education opportunities to empower the country's citizens and ensure sustainable socio-economic development by implementing strategies to use technology and improve education.

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